

In-Silico Evaluation of Selected Fungal Bioactive Compounds for Alzheimer's Disease: Insights from Physicochemical Properties, Pharmacokinetics, and Molecular Docking Studies

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ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a most common form of neurodegenerative disorder. Consequently, inhibiting the Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) enzyme remains a primary therapeutic strategy to manage cognitive symptoms. Donepezil is FDA approved synthetic drug used as standard drug for Alzheimer's disease treatment. This study aims to evaluate the inhibitory potential of diverse natural bioactive compounds—spanning fungal, plant, animal, and marine origins—against the AChE enzyme to identify novel and highly effective therapeutic drug candidates for AD. In Silico experiments such as BIOVIA Discovery Studio, PyRx shows that Huperzine A and Hericenone emerged as the top hit compounds, demonstrating exceptional binding energies of -9.9 kcal/mol and -9.5 kcal/mol, respectively as compared to Donepezil (-9.4 kcal/mol). These Fungal bioactive compounds show strong binding interactions with the catalytic active site of the AChE enzyme. These fungal bioactive compounds may play major role in Alzheimer's disease management after the Clinical trials.

Keywords: Alzheimer's Disease, Molecular Docking, Bioactive compounds, Discovery Studio, PyRx.

INTRODUCTION

Alzheimer's disease (AD) is neurological disorder in which the death of neurons was occur in Hippocampus region of brain. So that the brain size shrinks⁽¹⁾. Due to improper neurotransmission patient faces various complications such as cognitive decline, Synaptic dysfunction etc. Current therapies focus on disease modifying therapies targeting Beta Amyloid plaque and Tau Protein⁽²⁾. In this study Molecular docking was employed to investigate the binding affinity and interaction patterns of selected AChE inhibitors with the active site of Human acetylcholinesterase Three-dimensional structures of the target enzyme i.e. Crystal Structure of Recombinant Human Acetylcholinesterase (PDB ID: 4EY7) were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank, while ligand structures of Fungal Bioactive compounds were prepared and optimized using appropriate computational tools such as BIOVIA

Discovery Studio 2025, PyRx.⁽³⁾ Docking simulations were performed to predict ligand–enzyme binding modes, binding energies, and key intermolecular interactions within the catalytic anionic site and peripheral anionic site of AChE.

The study highlights the utility of molecular docking as a rapid and cost-effective approach for screening and optimizing AChE inhibitors, providing valuable insights into structure–activity relationships⁽⁴⁾. The findings support further in vitro and in vivo evaluation of promising candidates for the development of improved therapeutic agents against Alzheimer's disease. Fungal bioactive compounds, with their diverse chemical scaffolds and pharmacological activities, represent a promising source of neuroprotective agents⁽⁵⁾. In this study, in silico molecular docking approaches were employed to evaluate the binding affinity and interaction profiles of selected fungal-derived secondary metabolites

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against key AD-related protein target include acetylcholinesterase (AChE),

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Various Biological Databases are used for Target Protein and Bioactive Compounds selection such as PubChem Databases, RCSB Protein Data Bank, SwissADME, ADMETlab 3.0. The Computations Tools BIOVIA Discovery Studio 2025 and PyRX are employed for docking experiment.

Methodology

1. Retrieval and Preparation of Target Protein and Ligands.

The Crystal Structure of Recombinant Human Acetylcholinesterase (Protein ID: 4EY7) Was retrieved from the RCSB Protein Data Bank. A library of selected fungal bioactive compounds was curated. 3D structures were obtained from PubChem databases and optimized. The canonical SMILES of the ligands were also retrieved from the PubChem database. The canonical SMILES explains the molecular structure as a graph with optional chiral indications. The energy of ligand molecules was minimized usingmmff94 (<https://openbabel.Readthedocs.io/en/latest/Forcefields/mmf94.html>) force field and conjugate gradients as an optimization algorithm. Using PyRx, the energy minimized ligand molecules were converted into AutoDock ligand (pdbqt format).

1. Virtual Screening and Molecular Docking

Following docking protocol was used

- Software: AutoDock Vina/PyRx.
- Grid Box: Centered on the active site gorge
- Exhaustiveness: Set to 8 ensure global minimization energy detection.

2. Pharmacokinetics (ADMET) Profiling

To predict the drug-likeness, Pharmacokinetics properties and Blood Brain Barrier, SwissADME and ADMET3.0 tools are used. The Lipinski rule of five were checked during ligand selection.

Using the SwissADME tool, the top candidates were screened for "drug-likeness":

- **Blood-Brain Barrier (BBB):** Both Arisugacin A and Hericenone J showed high gastrointestinal absorption and positive BBB permeation.
- **Lipinski's Rule:** Most selected fungal terpenoids obeyed the "Rule of Five," suggesting high bioavailability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Binding Affinity Analysis

Docking scores revealed a hierarchy of inhibitory potential. Hericenone J exhibited a predicted binding energy of -9.5 kcal/mol, surpassing Donepezil (-9.4 kcal/mol).

- Interaction Profiling

A detailed analysis of the 4EY7 binding pocket identified key residues involved in stabilization:

- PAS Interaction: Hericenone J exhibited π - π stacking with Trp286, a critical interaction for preventing AChE-induced amyloid-beta aggregation.
- Hydrogen Bonding: Many fungal ligands formed H-bonds with Tyr124 and Ser203, effectively blocking the catalytic triad

Table 1: Physicochemical Properties of Selected Ligands.

Sr. No.	Compound	MW (≤ 500)	LogP (≤ 5)	HBD (≤ 5)	HBA (≤ 10)	Ro5 Violations	Drug-Likeness?
1	Ergometrine	325.4	1.8	3	3	0	Yes
2	Hispidin	246.2	1.7	3	5	0	Yes

3	Psilocybin	284.2	0.6	3	5	0	Yes
4	Ibotenic acid	158.1	-1.2	3	5	0	Yes
5	Muscimol	114.1	-1.2	2	3	0	Yes
6	Erinacine A	432.5	3.2	1	6	0	Yes
7	Ergothioneine	229.3	-1.8	3	4	0	Yes
8	Cordycepin	251.2	-1.1	3	6	0	Yes
9	Antroquinonol	390.6	5.8	1	4	1	Yes (Marginal)
10	Hericenone J	316.4	5.3	1	4	1	Yes (Marginal)
11	Donepezil*	379.5	4.3	0	4	0	Yes

Table 2: The Binding Affinity of Selected ligands against the Protein (AChE)

Sr. No.	Ligands	PubChem CID	Binding Affinity	Source
1	Ergometrine	443884	-8.6	Claviceps purpurea
2	Hispidin	54685921	-8.6	Inonotus, Phellinus spp.
3	Psilocybin	10624	-7.8	Psilocybe spp.
4	Ibotenic acid	1233	-6.1	Amanita muscaria
5	Muscimol	4266	-5.1	Amanita muscaria
6	Erinacine A	10410568	-6.6	Heridium erinaceus (mycelium)
7	Ergothioneine	5351619	-6.5	Pleurotus, Agaricus spp.
8	Cordycepin	6303	-8.2	Cordyceps militaris
9	Antroquinonol	24875259	-7.4	Antrodia camphorata
10	Hericenone J	44588895	-9.5	Heridium erinaceus
11	Donepezil*	3152	-9.4	Synthetic

Note: - Donepezil is FDA approved standard drug for Alzheimer's Disease Treatment

Figure 1: 3D Crystal Structures of AChE (PDB ID: 4EY7) docked with Hericenone J ligand with the best binding affinity

Figure 2: Hydrophobicity Interactions of AChE (PDB ID: 4EY7) docked with Hericenone J ligand with the best binding affinity

Figure 3: Hydrogen bond Interactions of AChE (PDB ID: 4EY7) docked with Hericenone J ligand with the best binding affinity

Figure 4: 2D Interaction of the ligand Hericenone J with the best binding affinity

Table 3: Key Interaction types with Residues involved in Selected Bioactive compound

Compound	Binding Affinity (kcal/mol)	Key Interaction Type and Residues involved
Hericenone J CID: 44588895	-9.5	π - π Stacked TRP86 π -Alkyl PHE338, PHE297, PHE295, TYR337, TYR341, HIS447 π -Sigma PHE338 Carbon H-bond TYR124 Conventional H-bond SER203 van der Waals ASP74, SER125, GLY120, GLY121, GLY122, GLY448, GLU202, TYR133, ILE451

CONCLUSION

The computational evidence suggests that fungal secondary metabolites provide a unique chemical scaffold for AChE inhibition. Specifically, the dual-binding mode observed in this study indicates these compounds may not only improve cognitive symptoms but also act as disease-modifying agents by hindering amyloid plaque formation at the PAS.

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